

Table 1: Distribution of the study population according to sociodemographic characteristics.

	Case (N=164)	Control (N=328)
Sex		
• Boys	91 (55.49% ; CI 95%=47.54-63.24%)	168 (51,22% ; CI 95%=45.83-56.58%)
• Girls	73 (44.51% ; CI 95%=36.76-52.46%)	160 (48.78% ; CI 95%=43.42-54.17%)
Recruitment period		
• July	3 (1.82% ; CI 95%=0.38-5.25%)	2 (0.6% ; CI 95%=0.17-2.20%)
• August	49 (29.87% ; CI 95%=22.99-37.51%)	95 (28.96% ; CI 95%=24.32-34.09%)
• September	43 (26.22% ; CI 95%=19.67-33.65%)	75 (22.86% ; CI 95%=18.65-27.71%)
• October	37 (22.56% ; CI 95%=16.41-29.73%)	71 (21.65% ; CI 95%=17.53-26.42%)
• November	26 (15.85% ; CI 95%=10.63-22.36%)	65 (19.82% ; CI 95%=15.86-24.47%)
• December	6 (3.66% ; CI 95%=1.35-7.79%)	20 (6.10% ; CI 95%=3.98-9.23%)

Table 2: Distribution of cases and controls according to the means of prevention (mosquito net and SMC) used.

	Cases (N=164)	Controls (N= 328)	P (p-value)
Mosquito net			
• Possession of a mosquito net	144 (85,80% ; CI 95%=79.7-90.9%)	298 (90,85% ; CI 95%=87.24-93.52%)	0,053
• Net use the day before the survey	128 (96.24% ; CI 95%=91.44-98.77%)	284 (99.65% ; CI 95%=98.06-99.99%)	0,007
Seasonal Malaria Chiomioprevention			
Taking of SMC	141 (85.98% ; CI 95%=79.7-90.9%)	322 (98.17% ; CI 95%=96.07-99.16%)	1.10 ⁻⁷
Last SMC			
• < 28 days	93 (68.38% ; CI 95%=59.86-76.08%)	246 (79.10% ; CI 95%=74.24-83.25%)	0,05
• 29-42 days	38 (27.94% ; CI 95%=20.59-36.28%)	58 (18.65% ; CI 95%=14.71-23.35%)	
• > 42 days	5 (3.68% ; CI 95%=1.20-8.37%)	7 (2.25% ; CI 95%=1.09-4.57%)	
Number of monthly treatments recieved			
▪ 0	44 (26.99% ; CI 95%=20.35-34.5%)	14 (4.27% ; CI 95%=2.56-7.04%)	1.10 ⁻⁴
▪ 1	39 (23.93% ; CI 95%=17.60-31.22%)	96 (22.56% ; CI 95%=16.41-29.73%)	
▪ 2	35 (21.47% ; CI 95%=15.44-28.58%)	83 (25.30% ; CI 95%=20.9-30.28%)	
▪ 3	27 (16.56% ; CI 95%=11.21-23.18%)	79 (24.09% ; CI 95%=19.77-29%)	
▪ 4	18 (11.04% ; CI 95%=6.68-16.89%)	56 (17.07% ; CI 95%=13.39-21.52%)	
Tablets delivered by CHW for D2 and D3	123 (82.55% ; CI 95%=75.49-88.27%)	317 (98.45% ; CI 95%=96.42-99.33%)	4.10 ⁻⁹

Taking the tablet at D2	109 (86.51% ; CI 95%=79.28-91.94%)	314 (98.43% ; CI 95%=96.38-99.33%)	1.10 ⁻⁴
Taking the tablet at D3	92 (73.02% ; CI 95%=64.38-80.53%)	307 (96.24% ; CI 95%=93.54-97.84%)	1.10 ⁻⁴
Mosquito net and SMC	60,97% (100)	84,45% (277)	0,032
